

Polarographic Behaviour of Xanthate Anions as Salts of 2,3-Dihydroxypyridine and 2-Amino-3-hydroxypyridinebis-(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) and -zirconium(IV) Chelates

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Bond *et al.*¹ studied the complex reduction mechanism for a series of cyclopentadienyl vanadium(IV) dithiolate complexes at dropping mercury electrode in which they observed one wave due to the presence of the free ligand. To examine the behaviour of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) and -zirconium(IV) complexes formed with 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) having some xanthates as anions associated with them, we have undertaken the present studies. It has to be noted that Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} in different media and pH are reduced at different potentials which leads in some cases even to non-observance of reduction wave².

Results and Discussion

When the solutions of $[(Cp)_2ML]^+ROCS_2^-$, where $M = Ti^{IV}/Zr^{IV}$; HL = DHP/AHP, R = Me, Et or i-Pr, were polarographed under experimental conditions, no cathodic wave was observed, indicating that $[(Cp)_2ML]^+$ species is not reduced at DME. But each complex species gave two anodic waves. The shapes of waves in all the complexes were nearly alike. Typical polarograms of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complex species are shown in Fig. 1. Wave-I is due to the oxidation of mercury electrode and formation of mercury salt with xanthate anion, while wave-II occurring at more negative potential, is assigned to be an adsorption wave arising from the formation of a thicker secondary film of insoluble $Hg(ROCS_2)_2$. The whole electrode process can be attributed to oxidation of mercury followed by rapid disproportionation to Hg^{II} and Hg.

Thus, $Hg(ROCS_2)_2$ is the final product of oxidation of Hg which has also been confirmed earlier³.

Fig. 1. Typical polarograms of (a) $[(Cp)_2TiL]^+EtOCS_2^-$; HL = DHP and (b) $[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+i-PrOCS_2^-$; HL = AHP.

The total height of the two waves gives constancy of $i_d/h_{eff}^{1/2}$ which indicates diffusion-controlled nature of overall electrode reaction. From the values of half-wave potentials (Tables 1 and 2) of first wave, it is clear that the half-wave potential of oxidation of mercury in substituted xanthate anions at d.m.e. follows the order $MeOCS_2^- > EtOCS_2^- > i-PrOCS_2^-$. This order is due to the ease of formation of the oxidation product $HgROCS_2$ in the order: $HgMeOCS_2^- < HgEtOCS_2^- < Hg i-PrOCS_2^-$. The electron-releasing order $CH_3 < C_2H_5 < i-Pr$ increasing the tendency of $ROCS_2^-$ to salt formation with mercury, may be responsible for the above order of ease of formation.

Experimental

All chemicals and reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The methods of preparation of the complexes were the same as reported in literature⁴.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF $[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ ROCS_2^-$ COMPLEXES

$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ ROCS_2^- = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO_3),
maximum suppressor : 0.005% gelatin, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Compd.	HL	$-E_{1/2}$ (v) vs SCE	
		Wave-I	Wave-II
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ MeOCS_2^-$	DHP	0.32	0.68
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ EtOCS_2^-$	DHP	0.30	0.69
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ i-PrOCS_2^-$	DHP	0.28	0.70
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ MeOCS_2^-$	AHP	0.30	0.69
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ EtOCS_2^-$	AHP	0.28	0.70
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ i-PrOCS_2^-$	AHP	0.27	0.72

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF $[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ ROCS_2^-$ COMPLEXES

$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ ROCS_2^- = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO_3),
maximum suppressor : 0.005% gelatin, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Compd.	HL	$-E_{1/2}$ (v) vs SCE	
		Wave-I	Wave-II
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ MeOCS_2^-$	DHP	0.30	0.67
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ EtOCS_2^-$	DHP	0.29	0.68
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ i-PrOCS_2^-$	DHP	0.28	0.69
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ MeOCS_2^-$	AHP	0.30	0.68
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ EtOCS_2^-$	AHP	0.28	0.70
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ i-PrOCS_2^-$	AHP	0.27	0.71

Polarograms were recorded using a galvanometer and a Leeds Northrup student potentiometer. A 40% methanolic solution of each compound ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) was prepared with the addition of required amounts of other components (0.1 M KNO_3 supporting electrolyte and 0.005% gelatin as maximum suppressor) for polarographic measurements. The temperature was kept constant at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. After deaeration, polarogram of each solution was recorded. The average current was recorded throughout the investigations. The dropping mercury electrode ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.03 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/2}$, $t = 3 \text{ s}$, $h = 40 \text{ cm}$ in 0.1 M KNO_3 in open circuit) and saturated calomel electrode were used.

References

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